

Sonifying Quantum Decoherence on IBM Quantum Devices: Mapping T1 Decoherence Values from Microseconds to Hertz

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Abstract. *This research aims to explore an innovative approach to understanding quantum decoherence through sonification. The plan is to audibly represent quantum decoherence by converting the median T1 value of an IBM Quantum device directly from microseconds to hertz. T1 values are indicative of the relaxation time that a qubit decoheres from state $|1\rangle$ to state $|0\rangle$ which reflects quantum decoherence. We will specifically focus on sonifying older generations of IBM Quantum devices by taking their median T1 values for the system and mapping them directly to hertz. This research not only facilitates an innovative way to physically listen to the phenomena of quantum decoherence, but provides an opportunity to hear the progression of pioneering quantum technology over time.*

1 Introduction

Quantum Decoherence and Quantum Information Science (QIS) remain relevant concepts for those curious to learn without a background in Physics, Mathematics, and Computer Science. [1] As someone who primarily has a background in music, who 14 months ago prior to the writing of this paper was new to QIS and a lot of STEM as a whole, there is a strong need for more comprehensive and digestible but accurate resources related to Quantum Decoherence and QIS. [2] While many professionals in academia, industry, and government agree on this need for a more comprehensive understanding of QIS, [3] which we see in efforts such as QuSTEAM, [4] or IBM Qiskit’s Quantum Explorers, [5] or even Quantum in Pictures, [6] these efforts are just the beginning for what the Second Quantum Revolution will look like. Demystifying and reimagining core concepts in QIS like Quantum Decoherence will allow those who are curious to learn more to create a solid foundation in differentiating between what I call various “quantum-nonsense” and real core concepts of QIS.

1.1 Quantum-nonsense

“Quantum-nonsense,” while not being a rigorous scientific term, describes media, television, musical, and artistic uses of the word quantum which functions more as a buzzword rather than describing a core concept in QIS. There are many examples of quantum-nonsense, but the most recent one at the time of this paper is “Spider-Man: Across the Spider-Verse” [7] which discusses later in the movie about a “quantum hole” that sucks an entire city into a deep dark void. From a researcher’s perspective or those who are heavily involved with the rigor of QIS, it might seem redundant to mention media portrayals of QIS since

it’s usually completely made up. But when one considers that “Spider-Man: Across the Spider-Verse” accumulated over half a billion U.S. dollars worldwide in a short time-frame, [8] perhaps a buzzword can be more counterproductive towards accurate educational attempts of QIS than previously considered. My research attempts to address the “quantum-nonsense” head on by utilizing valuable tools such as PureData and direct mapping of microseconds to hertz for understanding and interpreting phenomena such as quantum decoherence. Now while many researchers in QIS are very well aware that the quantum-nonsense exists, the more we can gather them and debunk them as a field, the higher chance we have of building an accurate and foundational understanding of QIS for those without a background.

2 Background

The background needed to understand my research is straightforward and simple with a light understanding of vectors, bra-ket notation, the Bloch sphere, qubits, quantum states, the difference between closed and open systems, T1 values, and hertz.

2.1 Vectors

Vectors have various meanings and connotations across Physics, Mathematics, and Computer Science. [9] This lends itself to appear significantly more confusing than it needs to be. A vector in many ways is similar to a line where it typically starts at the origin $(0, 0)$ which for vectors in QIS we typically represent in matrix form like this:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Which on a graph looks like this:

Though our vector isn’t really a vector yet, since it is just a point on the origin. But what if I wanted to graph a vector in matrix form that still was a 2x1 matrix having 2 rows and 1 column but wasn’t just a dot at the

origin? Intuition should make it pretty clear that we will move over 2 ticks on the x axis and one tick up on the y axis and draw a line to that point from the origin to get a vector that looks like this:

With all this being said, it is important to note that vectors can be in dimensions beyond \mathbb{R}^2 where the exponent just correlates to the dimension, and the \mathbb{R} refers to the set of all real numbers, which is a common notation in pure mathematics. If you have ever heard someone say that vectors are defined by having magnitude and direction, [10] basically the magnitude is the length or size of the vector and the direction of the vector is the direction the vector is facing in. If we wanted to be more detailed on calculating the exact magnitude of this vector, we would calculate something called the Euclidean norm, which is math that isn't necessary for this paper. Regarding calculating the direction of a vector, we would find the angle of the vector relative to that x-axis. In QIS we don't just use these vectors to create geometric representations like above but rather to define the quantum state mathematically.

2.2 Bra-ket notation

Bra-ket notation, or Dirac notation, is notation used in QIS to represent quantum states. [11] Classically, on a computer you would have a 0 or a 1, while in QIS we use fancier notation and call it $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$. If you've ever seen $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$ remember that they serve a different purpose than 0 or 1, since they have the "ket" notation on them, which indicates that in QIS we are talking about the quantum state as opposed to the classical state. [12] There is also the "bra" state that looks like this $\langle 0|$ and $\langle 1|$ which are just flipped "ket" states, hence bra-ket notation. Bra-ket notation is useful in QIS because $\langle 1| \neq |1\rangle$ but we can multiply them together like $\langle 1|1\rangle$ or any combination like $\langle 0|1\rangle$, $\langle 1|0\rangle$, or $\langle 0|0\rangle$ and we call that taking the inner product or the dot product. Relating this subsection to the previous one, we can go further and say that $|0\rangle$ is defined in QIS as the quantum state $|0\rangle$ which is really:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

and vice-versa $|1\rangle$ would be represented as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Now that we have discussed vectors and Bra-ket notation, we are ready to understand the Bloch Sphere which expands on both previous subsections.

2.3 Bloch Sphere

The Bloch Sphere was initially developed by Felix Bloch in 1946 as a tool to describe the behavior of nuclear spins in magnetic fields. [13] In QIS, the Bloch Sphere is a geometric representation of one single unit or bit of information, which in QIS we call a qubit. From this geometric representation, we can visualize a two-level quantum system where each level is either $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$ which are still mathematically the 2×1 vectors defined earlier. Take Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Bloch sphere representation of ket $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$.

This representation is common in physics and mathematics [14] and is useful to describe much of what is going on in the following subsections.

2.4 Qubits and Quantum States

A qubit is a quantum bit of information, where classical bits of information were 0 and 1, a qubit has two quantum states in $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ but can also be anything in-between on the Bloch Sphere. When I say quantum state, I am not only referring to the north and south pole, but we can have quantum states on a qubit that are anywhere else on the Bloch Sphere besides the north and south pole which are various combinations of $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$, and those quantum states are superposition states. This is where the fact of superposition being defined as a linear combination of vectors [15] starts to come together given the previous subsections. Let's say we want to graph a vector on the Bloch Sphere that is in the state $|0\rangle$, try to imagine what that would look like.

Figure 2 on the next page shows what that would look like to have a qubit in state $|0\rangle$. Figure 3 is a superposition state of state $|0\rangle$ and state $|1\rangle$ being a combination of our initial north and south pole quantum states. We can call $|0\rangle$ our ground state and $|1\rangle$ our excited state, which is useful in physics when we want to describe various energy levels of a particle. [16] A qubit can be an electron, a photon, an atom, or more just depending on what we are trying to analyze in QIS. [17]

Figure 2: Bloch sphere representation of ket $|0\rangle$.

Figure 3: Bloch sphere representation of one example of Superposition of $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$.

Digging deeper into this concept of having quantum states on qubits that can be $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$ or anything in between, the mathematical formalism leads us to:

A quantum state $|\psi\rangle$ of a qubit can be expressed as $|\psi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$, where α and β are complex probability amplitudes. [20] That statement is a lot without a background, so I will explain how each of those words, complex, probability, and amplitude, are all relevant to a quantum state of a qubit.

Complex numbers are in the form $a + bi$ where $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ and $i \in \mathbb{C}$. In other words, $a \in \mathbb{R}$ is saying that a is "contained in/an element of" a.k.a. \in of all real numbers a.k.a. \mathbb{R} . Same thing with the next statement except \mathbb{C} is all complex numbers, and bi represent a real number combined with i which is the imaginary number that mathematically is $\sqrt{-1}$. Combining real and imaginary numbers leads us to complex numbers where the real part is a and the imaginary part is bi .

Probability because our α and β are the probability we measure more or less of our basis states $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$, for example we might have something like:

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle$$

Just from seeing the equation above know that there is a 50/50 chance or probability that we have $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$. This is because probability always has to add up to 1, and to get our probabilities in our equation to add up to 1, we must square both $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ to get $\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}$ which of course equals 1. We have to square because of Born's Rule, which is a rule in QIS that lets us normalize the probability of getting either state $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$.

Amplitude because of more of the physics side of

QIS, in the sense that QIS has wave-particle duality, [18] and the amplitude in a complex probability amplitude is describing our wavefunction which is our quantum state $|\psi\rangle$.

The α and β are the complex probability amplitudes because it's just some combination of $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$ which formally are our basis states. Since all options of superposition in the Bloch Sphere will be some combination of $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$ we will just have a probability or a chance that our superposition will lean more towards $|0\rangle$ or more towards $|1\rangle$.

That is why when someone asks me what is one word I would use to describe QIS I always say "probability" and explain how you can have 50/50, 60/40, 70/30 etc. Because really initially in QIS, that is most of the "rigorous mathematics" you are doing.

2.5 Difference between open and closed systems

The distinction between open and closed systems is fundamental in understanding QIS. Closed systems are idealized models where the quantum states evolve in isolation, without any interaction with the environment. This simplifies the analysis and allows us to apply conservation laws, such as energy and momentum conservation. The behavior of closed systems is typically described by the Schrödinger equation, which gives the time evolution of the system's wavefunction. However, closed systems are largely theoretical constructs that lose their realism when implemented on the experimental side of QIS. Most of the formalism and subsections up until this point feature closed systems, while they might not be realistic, developing an intuition for closed systems provides a greater perspective on open systems.

In contrast, open systems are more representative of real-world quantum systems. In an open system, quantum states can interact with the environment, leading to effects such as decoherence. These interactions can cause a qubit to deviate from its intended state, introducing what we refer to as quantum noise. Furthermore, in an open system, we can control and measure the quantum states by interacting with the environment, which is how we perform operations on qubits and read out their states in a quantum computer. For example, consider a qubit in the form of a photon in an open system. If you are trying to measure the photon but an air particle interferes, that is an issue unique to open systems. Therefore, while the previous subsections have discussed closed systems, understanding open quantum systems is crucial for grappling with the complexities and real-life difficulties posed by quantum decoherence and quantum noise.

2.6 Quantum Decoherence/Quantum Noise

Quantum Decoherence is the decaying or deteriorating of a quantum state due to unwanted interactions with the environment that cause the sensitive quantum state to fall apart. These unwanted interactions with the environment appear in various ways, whether it be thermal fluctuations that provide enough energy to shift the excited state $|1\rangle$

to the ground state $|0\rangle$, or electromagnetic fields that also displace the quantum state. [20] Since IBM has superconducting qubits, they have open systems that experience the effects of quantum noise in the form of thermal fluctuations, electromagnetic fields, and defects in the material of the superconducting circuit. The superconducting circuit forms a two-level quantum system hence the excited state $|1\rangle$ and the ground state $|0\rangle$. The superconducting materials are typically made of aluminum, which when made into a superconducting material, can carry an electric current with zero resistance when cooled to very cool temperatures in the microkelvin. When IBM freezes their superconducting qubits to microkelvin, the effects of quantum noise through thermal fluctuations are reduced. This directly increases how long the quantum state lasts in microseconds and how long it takes to shift from the excited state $|1\rangle$ to the ground state $|0\rangle$. Even when frozen down to microkelvin, and most thermal excitations have largely been mitigated, there will still be smaller unwanted factors such as electromagnetic fields or material defects when increasing qubit size that will cause more errors and noise. For this reason, researchers focus on quantum error mitigation which is still developing research [21] as researchers attempt to mitigate thermal excitations, material defects, and electromagnetic fields to try to stretch out the quantum state to last longer than microseconds. Fault tolerant quantum computing would be a quantum computer that doesn't experience noise, and while that might be close to impossible, researchers are working on taking advantage of quantum error correction techniques such as this cooling of superconducting qubits to try to reduce the likelihood of disturbance from noise.

Quantum noise only exists in open quantum systems as opposed to closed quantum systems. This is because quantum noise is caused by the disturbances in the environment as described earlier, which is a trait only shared by open quantum systems. In closed quantum systems you have what are called pure states while in open quantum systems you have mixed states, since they are a mix of pure states. All mixed states are just various combinations (or superpositions) of pure states. We can use something called a density matrix to describe mixed states, think of density matrices in QIS as a tool that helps researchers find how 'densely packed' the probabilities are in a quantum state. Classically you had probability distribution while in quantum you have probability density.

For example, let's take our qubit in a superposition of $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$:

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$$

The density matrix ρ for this pure state is:

$$\rho = \begin{pmatrix} |\alpha|^2 & \beta\alpha^* \\ \alpha\beta^* & |\beta|^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Where $|\alpha|^2$ and $|\beta|^2$ are the probabilities of measuring the state $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ and the off-diagonal terms $\beta\alpha^*$ and $\alpha\beta^*$ capture the "coherence" between the states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$. When I say capture the 'coherence', I am refer-

ring to how the off-diagonal terms $\beta\alpha^*$ and $\alpha\beta^*$ when both 0, indicate that the mixed states in question are not coherent with each other. However if the off-diagonal terms are non-zero in a density matrix, it indicates that there is some level of coherence.

3 Sonification Method

The method of sonification is simple once T1 values of quantum decoherence and hertz are properly understood. The sonification of the IBM Quantum devices is a time to frequency mapping from microseconds to hertz. It is important to note that my research is directly mapping microseconds to hertz as opposed to considering time and frequency as reciprocals since the results are quite harsh to the ears. Here is an example:

To convert 220 microseconds to hertz, we need to consider the reciprocal relationship between time and frequency. Time and frequency are inversely proportional to each other.

Let's define the time period T in seconds, and the corresponding frequency f in hertz. The relationship between time and frequency is given by:

$$f = \frac{1}{T}$$

To convert microseconds to seconds, we divide the value by 10^6 since there are one million microseconds in a second. Therefore, 220 microseconds is equal to 220×10^{-6} seconds.

Substituting the time period T with 220×10^{-6} seconds, we can solve for the frequency f:

$$f = \frac{1}{220 \times 10^{-6}}$$

To simplify the expression, we can multiply the numerator and denominator by 10^6 :

$$f = \frac{10^6}{220}$$

Simplifying further, we find:

$$f \approx 4545.45 \text{ hertz}$$

Therefore, 220 microseconds is approximately equivalent to 4545.45 hertz when considering time and frequency as reciprocals.

Musically, 4545.45 hertz equates to about a D8, so the 8th octave in music, which is a whole step above the highest note on an 88-key piano. These pitches are strenuous on the ear, hence the direct mapping from microseconds to hertz so 220 microseconds is 220 hertz which is an A2, a pitch that is common and pleasant to hear. A large focus of the sonification is to be able to check where the T1 values are on the IBM Quantum devices whenever the IBM Quantum devices are calibrated.

3.1 T1 Values

T1 values in the context of quantum decoherence are the relaxation time in microseconds it takes for a quantum state to decohere from the excited state $|1\rangle$ to the ground state $|0\rangle$. Every IBM Quantum device has a T1 value for each qubit in any of their devices, which are calibrated multiple times a day, so therefore are dynamic and not static values. Not only does each qubit in an IBM Quantum device have it's own T1 value, but IBM Quantum devices as a whole have median T1 values. These median T1 values are what my research focuses on to sonify the phenomena of quantum decoherence, creating a way to physically hear what quantum decoherence sounds like.

3.2 Hertz

The unit of frequency in the International System of Units (SI) is hertz, denoted by Hz. [23] It is defined as cycles per second. When we speak of 'cycles' in the context of hertz, it essentially refers to the number of times a periodic event occurs per unit of time. For sound, this periodic event refers to the oscillation of the pressure wave that we perceive as sound.

Sound waves travel in cycles, where a cycle constitutes one full wave: starting at equilibrium, moving to a peak, returning to equilibrium, moving to a trough, and finally returning back to equilibrium. The number of these cycles that occur every second is the frequency of the sound wave, which is measured in hertz.

4 Demo

The two demos currently available are the Pure Data Demo used to represent the `ibm_perth` T1 Values from June 2023, and the Web App created with JavaScript and CSS all on my GitHub page. Pure Data is a visual programming language developed by Miller Puckette [24] in the 1990s created to interact with computer music in a unique way. The program is quite similar to MAX/MSP, [25] which was also developed by Miller Puckette. For a musical demonstration, I created a program where when you press a button, it will oscillate a value in hertz that correlates directly to the T1 value or the median T1 value of an IBM Quantum device. Since I am unable to show that demo in a research paper, the reader is always welcome to explore the GitHub repository link and try the web app for themselves. [26]

5 Future Work

Future work for this project entails plans to create an interactive museum exhibit at the Museum of Science and Industry [27] in Chicago, IL. The plan is to develop an iOS app that will serve as a prototype for the museum, and perhaps other museums. It will be a larger touchscreen device, with a color scheme similar to IBM's computing resources and 'Map View' more specifically, with the same spectrum of purple, white, and blues that are used for IBM Quantum devices visually. It is a goal to have the button be pressed at the museum and retrieve the median T1 value in real time

by contacting IBM's server and collecting that info in real time.

Besides an educational approach at a museum, future work would be not only implementing T1 values, but T2 values as well. There is no specific reason that my research focuses on T1 only and not T2 values, but this is a place for future work, along with collecting all the median T1 values of older IBM Quantum devices to show the progression of quantum technology over time.

Another opportunity for future work would be similar to IBM's Quantum Music Playground with Jim Weaver and Brian Ingmanson [28] involving a presentation entitled "The Sound of Quantum Decoherence", that I would present in various museums and universities around the world.

Since the writing of this paper I have also been exploring what in the lab or in QIS could be sonified that I hadn't thought of before, and one idea would be the Zeeman levels of $\text{Yb}+171$. Since these energy levels are in the mega hertz, the sonification would obviously need to be scaled so that humans could hear it, but I think it is a possibility of further research on what regarding an auditory experience could inform researchers in physics and STEM as a whole.

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7 Conclusion

It is evident that there is a lot of work to be done on continuing to create comprehensive and digestible but accurate resources for QIS. My research on "The Sound of Quantum Decoherence" put more simply, is but a starting point for the potential to educate and inspire more attention and thought to the fields of QIS and music. My goal with the section 2 was to be as thorough and clear as possible to explain the fundamentals of QIS that lead to the understanding of quantum decoherence and my sonification research. As our field of QIS grows and develops rapidly, maintaining creativity and perspective will prove to be valuable assets moving forward.

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